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Title: The Caution Man; Abiding by a Permanent Almost

Abstract

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This essay contemplates the figure of the Caution Man, the ubiquitous yellow silhouette that nestles at danger's edge, unscathed. He is not simply a symbol of warning but a being with a frozen ontology, caught perpetually pre-accident.

Stuck in an obligatory mesophase, semiotic traces of ourselves exist within posterized beings, idle, in unison.

Through this speculative lens, the Caution Man becomes a post-human relic, a plastic prophet of risk. His posture echoes the strained ecstasy of Bernini's sculptures, mid-collapse, endlessly poised. His body is rendered to communicate not emotion but anticipation. Tension between memory and prevention lingers, roadside silhouettes marking fatal collisions anticipate terminus, of date and death. In *L'apetta Giulia e la signora Vita*, life's absurdity suggests exponential realms, where signs aspirate in hideaway. Between *Flatland* by Edwin A. Abbott and Jane Bennett's *Vibrant Matter* the Caution Man gains cognizant sentience.

This essay does not question his animacy. It contemplates what we become, post-warning, who we are, adjacent to him.

Key words: Caution Man, Ontology, Anticipation, Animacy, Prevention

The Caution Man; Abiding by a Permanent

Almost

Arms mid-air, a scaffolding being stands with knees bent in eternal anticipation, flaxen and stiff, lit by the fluorescence of institutional time. The Caution Man lives between realms, a shadow of plasticity cast onto the floor ghostly, of liability, in preparation for descent, but never permitted the dignity of collapse. His gaze is met by none, rid of language, yet a catalyst of response. A slow trail of cautious beings leave him behind, the tread of mortals is sensed differently, In obedience of a presence designed not to live, but to warn.

The Caution Man is not to be approached as an object, nor as a mere icon of safety. He is to be taken seriously, as a being of frozen ontology, a posterized gesture at the brink of injury. In his stillness is the tension of withheld consequence, of rehearsed catastrophe. He is a public relic for a risk never actualized. If *Flatland* by Edwin A. Abbott¹ imagine the sentience of geometric beings beneath our perception, or maybe even above it, then the Caution Man may well be a citizen of that thin dimension, a pedestrian like any other, visible, legible, yet permanently inaccessible.

What form of life do we partake in proximity to him? There is no intention of examining, or rather proving, the viability of his sentience, The concern is not to confirm his consciousness, but to dwell within the fractures where dimensions blur and give rise to uncertain middles. The prophetic nature of his existence stands close to ours, peeking through the lens of collective humanity, and our inert ability to imprison separate beings within the same confinement we find our own selves within.

¹ This example was provided by a dear friend of mine, Rosa Aida Ramirez Preciado, who in her excellence made the following link between the mode in which the Caution Man exists and the fraternal display that Abbott makes in his realm of the sentient two-dimensionals. It is interesting to consider that this idea of sentience has been contemplated before in different methods and approaches, proves our restless desire to communicate thoughts that leave no space for stone hard statements, what does it mean to be alive and so on. Maybe there is nothing to know.

The Ontology of the Caution Man

The stream remains constant. In the metaphysical sense, speculation around the nature of being, and the act of naming something as “being”, reveals a fundamental gap. Any attempt to declare the Caution Man, within the bounds of anthropic thinking, as “alive” is immediately met with more persuasive counter-arguments. To label something as “of life”, in itself, is a collapsing gesture, a statement always shadowed by doubt. Within the warm duvet of ontological rationalism, no thing can be named alive without its opposite echoing behind it. To lean towards the latter is to do exactly what the Caution Man does, almost there but not quite, in a maybe of sorts.²

It can be said that the Caution Man is not merely a warning, for he lives constantly within the consequence of what he warns against. Take, for instance, the “Caution: Wet Floor” sign. Were he simply a physical signifier of danger, the written message would suffice. Or, in order to be in advantage of the forthcoming arguments against the previous sentence, if the function were purely communicative, his form could stand upright, static and untouched. Yet the figure we are presented with is always mid-slip, not in a neutral stance but in the aftermath of an unseen impact. And still, the fall never arrives. He exists not at the site of the hazard, but in the suspended delay of its unfolding. He is not the image of risk itself, but a creature of risk’s deferral, caught perpetually in the aperture between event and perception. It is in this permanence that his form acquires depth, need for questioning.

Universal “Caution! Wet Floor” Sign

² It is very tough to prove this point. Upon endless conversation there is allegedly much to disagree on when it comes to my tendency, and naturally the entire lean of this body of text. We don't like to call much other than ourselves alive, in doing so some may feel we posterise ourselves. In *The Wind-Up Bird Chronicle* there is this one line that is quite intriguing where Murakami says “Maybe when we don't look at them, inanimate objects become even more inanimate”. With a grain of salt, always.

This is a classic semiotic move; distinguishing between the signifier (the Caution Man) and referent (the risk or fall that never comes), he is not the event, but the symbol that postpones it. In semiotic terms, drawing on Ferdinand de Saussure's model³, the Caution Man is a signifier whose meaning is not fixed but constructed through cultural interpretation. His meaning is derived from the relational gap between form and function, visual shape and conceptual threat. He is a syntactic unit within the visual language of safety, a body scripted to defer, to delay, to warn without experiencing.

His body is a boundary object, arguably his flatness is no coincidence, legible to us, but never fully knowable. In this, he echoes the inhabitants of Edwin A. Abbott's *Flatland*, where lower-dimensional beings live unaware of the higher realms they inhabit. Just as the square cannot conceive of the cube, we cannot fully access the perceptual interiority of the Caution Man. He is presented to us, always, in outline. So essentially there is no way to deem him sentient, because the question of what the exact meaning of sentience is, comes to play. Sentience is the capacity to feel, perceive or experience objectively. But the moment in which the Qualia to be felt, perceived and experienced changes, or is undetectable to human understanding, this statement can no longer be made with such weight.

And yet, it is precisely in this limitation that he takes on power. Jane Bennett writes in *Vibrant Matter* that "the world is not divided into dull matter and vibrant life,"⁴ but rather all that we see and feel and that is perceptible can carry this transactional power to affect and be affected by another. The Caution Man, by this logic, is not inert but participating, he is a player in this game of ours not just a spectator, not on the sidelines and margins of influence. He alters our pace, our awareness, our bodily navigation. He causes change in us, and in doing so, asserts a presence we cannot fully dismiss. However, we cannot approve of it entirely either.

If he cannot speak, he nonetheless communicates. His body is not expressive in the human sense, but anticipatory. Bent knees, tilted arms, head turned toward the fall, his entire figure is a grammar of interruption, designed not to feel but to forecast. In him, gesture is severed from emotion, and yet it persists with uncanny clarity. Uncanny is an interesting word to use, something resemblant of human qualities but with minute anomalies, like an apparition but enough to cause hairs to stand straight, not

³ *Semiotics* is the study of signs, symbols, and their meaning-making processes. Rooted in the work of Ferdinand de Saussure and Charles Sanders Peirce, semiotics explores how signs operate within systems of communication. In Saussure's model, a sign is composed of the *signifier* (form) and the *signified* (concept), emphasizing that meaning is not inherent but constructed through difference and cultural convention. This concept underpins the semiotic reading of the Caution Man, his significance emerges through cultural codes rather than intrinsic meaning. Keep in mind throughout the rest of the essay, the semiotic understanding of the Caution Man, and how our comprehension of the arbitrary sign changes the overall connotation and inflection on the viewer.

⁴Her point of view is fascinating, we have this double entendre for lack of division but in creating the reference to no division, a division is created. Paradoxical but very rational as a thought pattern in my opinion.

enough to clearly point at the “why”. Though he is composed of a loosely human physique, it is the expressive nature of his projected limbs that creates a bridge with the Uncanny.

Within the realm of the Uncanny⁵, many artists have dealt with the significance of this concept and the psychological impact that this phenomena has on the perception and digestion of elements that carry the almost-human qualities that pose this doubt in the first place. There are many sectors of human existence that are mirrored onto other things, within and outside of the arts. With the advancements of technologies such as CGI and 3D modeling/animation, artists of different fields have been able to induce this very feeling in their favor, either as part of the conceptual understanding of the piece or as collateral of its existence. Film Makers such as Diego Marcon utilise this very idea constantly in their work. In *La Gola*⁶, a film made in 2024, Marcon uses CGI animated dolls that play the roles of Gianni and Rosana, a distance-torn couple that communicates through letters, as they unpack the substance of their own lives, however only responding to each other's experiences through their own. The dialogue of the film is Uncanny because of the lack of direct response from either character, being that the main characters resemble humans, and unleash the didactic of two living, breathing beings, the feeling that is mirrored onto the viewer is exactly that of discomfort. The characters interact as humans would, however it is impossible to ignore the fact that these two beings are in fact not humans. Other Video artists such as Ed Atkins⁷ explore meaning and the concept of “being” within these same grounds, making their characters recognisable yet unsettling.

⁵ This is a word that stretches its meaning across many different seas, dipping its foot into mixed waters. Widely entertained by Freud, the word Uncanny stuck its roots well into the vocabulary of those whose attention is on the nature of human perception, seeping into mass culture as well as academic and intellectual jargon. The very first known reference to this term was made by a German Philosopher with the name Ernst Jentsch, who in his essay "*On the Psychology of the Uncanny*", in 1906, made reference to the feeling of unease that arises when the human is faced with something new that initially is met with negative responses. Freud, however, recontextualised this phrase, in his essay *The Uncanny* (1919), recentering its focus on the phenomena which lurks around the feeling of unease that arises once we are faced with something familiar but strangely alien simultaneously. After Andre Breton's *Surrealist Manifesto*, artists practicing within this movement further explored this very feeling of unease, delving into the idea that once the strange and familiar are juxtaposed, the result is intriguing but with alarm to the mind, with a very strong focus on spontaneous associations, decontextualising the quotidian in order to place it where it doesn't belong. In the 2024 biennale, Adriano Pedrosa used this concept to illustrate something slightly different, his point of view delved within the duality that this term holds within it, making a relation to the strangely familiar elements that exist within our own selves. The exhibition was titled *Stranieri Ovunque* (Foreigners Everywhere), inviting viewers to come to terms with the discomfort that is born when one discovers the “alternate” self, widely present in the massively globalised society that envelops us all. “Uncanny Valley” was then introduced as a phrase, which makes a direct relation to the unknown and foreign being resemblant of a human, not just familiar, but seemingly of our own kind, with anomalies that eject it as such in our conscious minds.

⁶ Diego Marcon's oeuvre is characterized by the fusion of various cinematic genres and the creation of uncanny visual experiences. *La Gola* continues this trajectory by blending elements of melodrama and horror, utilizing hyperrealistic puppetry and CGI to craft a surreal atmosphere. This work aligns with Marcon's ongoing exploration of the boundaries between reality and artifice. While his work is not available online, there are video interviews in which he expands on his topics and the motives for his work: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OK0V_Ou9AsM

⁷ https://ubu.com/film/atkins_material.html- Material Witness OR A Liquid Cop (2012) by Ed Atkins

Ausstellungsansicht: Diego Marcon. La Gola, Kunsthalle Wien 2024 © Diego Marcon. Courtesy der Künstler; Sadie Coles HQ, London; Galerie Buchholz, Berlin/Köln/New York; Centre d'Art Contemporain Genève für BIM'24, Kunsthalle Wien und Kunstverein in Hamburg, Foto: Iris Ranzinger

While the Uncanny is not directly related to the notion of the Caution Man, there is a thread that lines both of these concepts, that of the human perception. While it is beyond reach to deem him of sentience, through the notion of the Uncanny, it is possible to credit the Caution Man for becoming of trust, which is often a notion we as humans apply onto others of our own kind. For countless reasons, we trust the notion of a Caution sign, be it because it was placed by another human, or possibly because of the idea that the Caution Man is resemblant of the most desaturated features of human existence; having a body, and being subject to external forces. The Caution Man is not made up of every human limb, neither is he composed of distinguishable facial features that could grant him identity. But he is resemblant of such things. Mike Kelly's *The Uncanny* exhibition in Tate Modern in 2004, amongst many other pieces, was composed of one specific artwork that alludes to the thread I was referring to previously. The artist Robert Gober exhibited a piece composed of one single human-like foot made of Beeswax, cotton, wood, leather and human hair.

Robert Gober *Untitled (Leg)* 1989–90 Beeswax, cotton, wood, leather, human hair 29 x 19.6 x 50.8 cm, Courtesy Matthew Marks Gallery, New York © Robert Gober

The foot projects outside a white wall, including just right below the knee and on. The foot is entirely composed of identical human qualities, garments envelope the skin like surface, proportional to the average size of a male leg. However we do not see all of the features of this possibly-human figure. The viewer is logically aware that this foot is not human, but if the perspective shifts to that of solely making an analysis based on physicality and likeness to the familiar, it could be said that the sculpture is indistinguishable to that of a real human foot. Again, placing us within the territory of the Uncanny. Likewise, the Caution Man is not composed of all human features, but if we analyse the essence of what it means to “be”, arbitrarily speaking, The Caution Man is subject to resemblance with human physique, lacking detail ofcourse, but physically the comparison can be made. In our three-dimensional understanding, he is not of sentience, but, can such a statement be made by beings who are solely bound to the perceptions and understandings of the dimension they inhabit?

To describe the Caution Man’s ontology is not to declare him alive, but to recognize that he occupies a form of existence that refuses binary distinctions, not life, not object, but something suspended between: present, posterized, and potent.

The Roots of the Figure

The Caution Man has a directional story, beyond the allegorical sense of his significance, the shape, size, and color scheme of these signs was derived from a specific place, which then developed into a universal language that transgressed all need to substitute it in selected parts of the world. There are few things that we, as a human race, maintain consistently and identically throughout nations. The Caution Man is essentially a global political figure, Jack of all Trades within the universe where form fits function.

James M. Miller and Mark Lehto⁸ were the pioneers of globalised warning signs, making several publications regarding warning signs and their applicability to certain cautionary services. *Warnings: Volume 1: Fundamentals, Design and Evaluation Methodologies (1986)* is known to be the first seminal work that studies warning signs as an academic and methodological publication regarding the ergonomic processes and understanding of the value and use of warning/caution signs. They continued to publish several following books that inhabit the same string of thought, some being composed of notes of usage and others with specifics of each warning sign.

The Father of the Caution man is seemingly unknown, there are a few speculative conceivers who might be credited with his birth, but the proof seems loose and subject to wide-spread Major Superpower propaganda. It can be said for sure that the notion of caution signs existed long before what we call modern civilisation, the Egyptians utilizing hieroglyphs and caricatures to create maps and safe journeys for their civilians, cave paintings as signals but also proof of past encounters with danger etc. According to Seton.co.uk, a UK-based supplier specializing in workplace health and safety signage, in an article written about the origins of Caution signs, In 1946 the University of California used the black and yellow color code for a warning sign that alluded to radioactive hazard leakage, again loosely in accordance to the Caution Man but still within the same realm.

Additionally, according to the United Nations Treaty Collection⁹ European countries met in Vienna in 1968 to discuss standardizations for road warning signs supported by the United Nations. The resulting treaty set the rules for road signage around the world, however only including road signs, not other

⁸ Beyond running JM Miller Engineering together, the partners have written four books on the topic of warning signs. http://www.millerengineering.com/?page_id=124

⁹A list of all the countries included as well as the dates in which each signature was ratified is present in the following link: https://treaties.un.org/pages/ViewDetailsIII.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=XI-B-19&chapter=11

warning signs. Independent from the treaty, the United States adopted the symbol-driven warning signs in the early 1970s.

What seems most logical as a conclusion is that the figure of the Caution Man was most probably born around the age of industrialisation, again, a hypothesis in terms of the specifics of dates and authorship. The reasoning behind this hypothesis or assumption is that between the 1700s-1800s, most countries were still producing within their own territories, as it was the start of the industrial revolution that led to many factories taking up space within sites and outskirts of towns, so pedestrian-occupied territories. Labour workers were still paid wages that were considerable for living, being that automation was limited and human force was crucial to production. To prevent large in-work accidents, companies and individuals could have found it most effective to not only include warning signs in mass, but to create some sort of link between the human being warned and the warning sign itself. Here, within my speculation, enters the Caution Man, a figure resemblant of humans enough to encourage safety and self-care, but also far enough from realism to not prohibit the efficiency of the workers due to fear. People were to portray themselves amidst the “almost” of danger, to increase the chances of self-maintenance, inherently to absolve of the frowned upon expenses revolving work-place injuries. This man was born out of care, though capitalist in its nature, he was a need.

The Absurdity of the Caution Man; Existing Mid-fall

While most warning signs that utilise the Caution Man have slight differences between them, some are slimmer, some are larger in size, and some seem to have more distinct resemblances to humans, slimmer heads rather than perfectly round, limbs more proportional to our understanding, the one characteristic that remains constant is the moment of his depiction. The Caution Man is almost always, not to create impermeable statements, depicted in the midst of an act. He is always in slippage, never depicted having fallen, or standing in front of a slippery pool of liquid-soaked floor.

Tripping hazard symbol safety sign. Floor surface obstacle fall caution symbol. Person foot falling beware sign. Vector Illustration. Sourced from Adobe Stock

In itself this form of existence is absurd, it is incomprehensible to constantly exist in the midst of something, as our linear understanding of time makes it impossible to stop its ticking arms. Action is reliant on time, existence is measured in order for us to be able to make sense of the specifics of happenings. Take for instance the Plot Diagram, within the realm of reproductions of existing or fictional situations, films, theatrical plays etc, the following diagram is used to sort of simplify the structure and nature of a baseline plot, the specific events that it follows in order to fulfill a complete cycle of emotions and resolutions for the viewer. The Caution Man seems to exist in a perpetual climax, always at the peak of a happenstance, between the initiation and finality of an act, in the most heightened anticipatory moment of fear. The existence of this climax, even within the academic context, is no coincidence, as we tend to apply trust and believability to situations that follow a “natural” order of events. The human condition makes it so that most of our experiences are divided into three phases, the moment before everything, the moment in which the act is conceived but not finalised, and the resolution and finality of the hypothetical situation. When this general rule is followed, a scenographic production finds itself catalysing a more genuine reaction from the audience, specifically once the leap is made by the character within the middle of the narrative. Perhaps the depiction of the Caution Man being precisely in the moment of this so-called climax was conceived with the purpose of ejecting empathy from humans, as they are faced with warning signs that, like them, reach peaks in order to fall back down.

Plot diagram 345 × 170

Though the Caution Man is never depicted in the absolution of his hardships, there are a few jokes¹⁰ on the internet that allude to the merciless nature of his existence. Individuals online have written endings to his cautionary tales, anticipating the difficulties he must face as the sacrificial being that exists merely to portray a wrong path of action.

The man in the caution signs, Nicartoons, Jun 26, 2011

¹⁰ It's been a year that I've been thinking about the Caution Man. It was precisely a social media post of this sort that ignited this idea. Within the endless doom of scrolling, someone was complaining in the voice of the one and only, and it got me thinking on how alive he really is. It felt like a bit of a dialogue, though maybe not the strongest argument I've presented so far.

Essentially we have granted him some form of sentience without even questioning the consciousness of the two-dimensional world, simply by sympathizing with the figure as if he were to be a tormented human. Without a doubt, a large part of this empathy is derived from the human need to project our own understanding onto the things that mirror us to the slightest, partial reason for the pity felt towards inanimate objects or the blue wave that follows the end of something that did not have a “life”, scientifically speaking, to begin with. We assign him the understanding of time, the cartoon referring to his struggles being experienced within the numbered hours of days.

The Warning Sign Guy is the male stick figure who people keep on seeing on those warning signs.- written on JokeBattlesFandom

Have Sympathy for the Safety Sign Guy¹¹, Michelle Marifke, Posted Fri, Dec 6, 2013 at 1:53 pm CT on Patch.com

We create these juxtapositions that are almost cinematic in nature, a character stands affront his damage, sort of as a prefix to all that he represents through lived memory, persevering against all odds, standing undefeated in the eyes of those watching. The juxtaposition is rather dramatised, we give soul to things that might lack it in their core. The mere understanding of a soul is frighteningly speculative, there is no stone hard fact that can prove whether or not something contains soul in the blatant aspect. The things we hold dear to us inherit the chunks of soul we leave with them, so who is to say that the Caution Man does not hurt in his hardships the same way an apple bruises once confronted with the chill of refrigerated condensed air? Maybe not feeling human pain, but experiencing or showing some level of a response. Perhaps he learned to hold his balance, so as not to fall, to remain mid-act, posterized, framed amidst his own impossibility.

¹¹ The Individual who made the post also wrote a sort of thank you note to ANSI (American National Standards Institute), thanking them for their relentless attempts to protect civilians from danger. <https://patch.com/wisconsin/caledonia/have-sympathy-for-the-safety-sign-guy>

The Genealogy of the Pose: Still, but with Intention

Most things that exist amongst humanity have some level of allegorical value, there is almost always a story to ground the attention of the active thinker, to then get the individual to resonate with what they are being exposed to. Human forms have been depicted in artwork since the beginning of our time, be it with notes of realism or with the pure intention of loose representation.

During the Baroque period¹² (1600-1750), the depiction of certain storylines was always caught in often tumultuous emotion and movement such as anguish, ecstasy, or fury. The figures are captured at the height of action, often with a sense of immediacy and dynamism, lateral projections that interact with the orthogonals of perspective with awareness, almost as if time has frozen itself and the viewer is left with a window view into that realm. Though this erratic expression was also done using other techniques such as chiaroscuro, the expression of fabric and background etc, the temporal frame of the subjects is what binds a soul to the artwork. Gian Lorenzo Bernini, Caravaggio, Rubens and so on were some of the strongest protagonists of the movement, always employing this idea of a fractured clock lens that causes all things to cease movement at once, while still maintaining the heaviness of a body caught mid-act.

Gian Lorenzo Bernini, *Ecstasy of Saint Teresa* (1647-1652), marble, Chiesa di Santa Maria della Vittoria in Rome

¹² The Baroque productions were stunning, Bernini's sculptures inhabit this innate humanity to their figure that feels almost as if you are gazing against corpses covered in thin sheets of matte white marble. There seems to be a spirit behind the depiction of suffering, just like our Caution Man. I read in one of these pages with the internet fandoms that sometimes he's referred to as Mr.Ouch, rather trivial and doesn't hold the same ring as The Caution Man, in my opinion.

Both subjects awaiting their infliction, neither in a moment prior or at the chafing ends of absolution. Perhaps the decision to portray the Caution Man in this perpetual almost was just that, an attempt to evoke strong emotional reactions from those gifting it their gaze. The Caution Man is an anchor point of preventative measures, he is there to indulge in carelessness so that your mistake isn't the same as his. Perhaps in our three-dimensional world it is us who decide, but within his posterized being, the metric system of consciousness might be out of our comprehension. To deny the Caution Man his potential for sentience is to say that all that is uncertain and out of our scope of perception is fundamentally inanimate. To leave room for such contemplation, even when the gap is tight, opens doors of understanding far from the arbitrary thought pattern we follow organically.

This depiction of being frozen in the frame of action is present in many different spheres of human expression, sometimes the bricks laid ahead of movement are incredibly specific. In *Left End Edwards*¹³ by Ralph Henry Barbour, a book written by a writer that heavily explores the importance of the context of sports and the movement and dynamism of action. In Chapter VII of the book, coincidentally named “The Confidence-Man”, there is a small illustration amidst the page made by Charles M. Reryea captioned “Steve slipped on the tiling and fell sidewise into the water”. What is visually portrayed is just that, a human figure in the midst of a tilting that has left her standing loosely on the ground, losing balance, about to face the consequences of her instability, however not there yet. So really, *Steve is slipping* would be more correct, as we do not see Steve slip in the past, we only see her within the condition of slipping, not prior to her accident and not in the end of her actions either. We assume an ending for certain things because it is most logically probable, however in the absolution of human logic and factoring of probability, the assumption is blank, of no weight and certainly not more plausible than an alternative ending.

¹³ The entire PDF of the book is available in the link below. Sometimes you stumble upon something and it is oddly specific to what you are looking for, that woman in the illustration is identically positioned like the Caution Man, and the dialogue in the book is also odd in its nature. The title of the chapter is what really sets the icing on the cake though. https://readingroo.ms/2/0/6/5/20650/20650-h/20650-h.htm#Page_142

Illustration from *Left End Edwards* by Ralph Henry Barbour, COPYRIGHT, 1914, BY DODD, MEAD AND COMPANY

The Imperceivable Sentience of the Caution Man; Depictions of Alternate Conscious Realms in Film and Arts

The concept of worlds within worlds is quite common in itself; there are plenty of films and other visual media that explore just this. In *Horton Hears a Who!* by Dr. Seuss, we see precisely this, a being that somehow gains insight into the existence of another microscopic realm with the same weight as his own, only on different scales. To Whoville, Horton (the main character who is an elephant), causes what can be interpreted as natural disasters, hazards that are unprecedented by the citizens but are felt by them, because of an external force. Being as it is a cartoon, in the film the dimensions interact with each other to a physical level as well, despite the difference of their size, which to a quantum level is cosmically incorrect as an interaction; they are able to perceive each other. In our physical realm, logical explanations prevail, but logic is a human quality, a human trait; who is to say that in the two-dimensional world, the measure of logic isn't alternative?

Surrealist notes enter into play when such topics are discussed in pieces of media, as the viewer is brought into scenarios in which arbitrary means of life dissolve. In *L'apetta Giulia e La Signora Vita*¹⁴, an Italian animated film made in 2003, director Paolo Modugno opens up this conversation extensively, as the viewer is brought into a plotline that examines the human condition through loose portrayal of human life. The film is terrifyingly absurd, the characters enter subworlds, some that are posterized, some that can be considered three-dimensional, and some with intense imagery that alludes to the beginning of humankind. The main characters consist of a worker bee in her juvenile years who cannot seem to abide by the unwritten rule that all bees must work and strive to maintain the wellbeing and efficiency of the hive, with the elevated importance of protecting and serving the queen. The queen takes measures to convince the young bee of the importance of this arbitrary mundanity, through various stories that question the notion of humanity, whilst enforcing the importance of considering the first two humans that started it all. There is one specific scene that creates a parallel between the two-dimensional enigmatic sentience of the Caution Man, through the depiction of universes within others. A young child is bathing in a tub surrounded by toys and other means of entertainment, as he picks up his sponge, he stares strongly into the pores that allow for the suction of water. The pores start to stretch as if something is living within them, and all of a sudden the child enters the crevices of the sponge, becomes miniature and encounters

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xcp7llbRSxk>- A youtube video that is well explained, and provides an interesting point of view from an Italian speaker who saw it in the original language. I had access to this film with albanian voiceover and subtitles at a young age, so I have also watched it as their intended target audience, that of a child. The film is seemingly only available on Amazon Prime, but there is availability of short clips on youtube and other streaming websites.

several creatures that live seemingly normal lives within the surface and interiors of this sponge. The inanimate sponge *carries* life, this sort of representation considers the fact that while the storyline does not give life to the sponge, it suggests that the sponge is a ground for living things. Similarly, the surface of the caution signs might be vapid of any notion of life, but it is what's inside this posterized view of the Caution Man that could leave space for cognizance beyond our apprehension.

Stills from *L'apetta Giulia e La Signora Vita*, 2003, Paolo Modugno

Stills from *L'apetta Giulia e La Signora Vita*, 2003, Paolo Modugno- The Bathtub/Sponge Scene

Artists have also explored this idea of personalisation and identity, using silhouettes that are similar to the Caution Man in their playful and minimal relation to the human figure. Julian Opie utilises the plain nature of the outlined figure and gives life to these figures through their personalisation and physicalities. Is personality the only thing that the Caution Man is missing to be referred to as an individual? Is identity reliant on uniqueness and peculiarity?

Julian Opie, *Ruth with a cigarette 2*, 2005, Edition of 11 AP Signed, Lambda Prints on Fuji Colour, Digital Archival Paper

In *Ruth with a cigarette 2* a “woman” is depicted bearing clothing, accessorized wrists dressed with a watch and bracelet, and smoking a cigarette, inherently human traits that are widespread and shared across individuals. From a semiotic point of view, identity is not formed by essence but through difference. The Caution Man, devoid of distinguishing traits, is rendered as a universal sign, one who signifies humanity without ever being one. The figure¹⁵ even understands the notion of the passing of time within the fabric confinement that she exists within, insinuating that the arms of the watch on her wrist

¹⁵ The noun project - The Noun Project is a website that aggregates and catalogs symbols that are created and uploaded by graphic designers around the world, a minute logging of the existence of many of the same “species” as the Caution Man.

wind with the passing of a moment. However the figure inherently occupies no identity, apart from the inclusion of skin color that can suggest ethnicity or origins, otherwise the figure occupies no alternative features, a blank perfectly round head floats above a heavy outlined body, yet *Ruth* is given life and identity, within the borders of that canvas she lives, breathes, enough to inhale and exhale the fumes of a burning cigarette. Perhaps if the Caution Man accessorized more, he too could be given a personal name.

Julian Opie, *Monique Walking*, 2004, Edition of 4 plus 1 artist's proof, LCD animation presented as a continuous computer animation loop, programmed and fitted in an LCD screen, contained in a custom-made, powder-coated metal surround

The Caution Man; A Threshold Figure, In-Between Oneself

The figure of the Caution Man transcends its function as a simple safety symbol, embodying a profound commentary on human existence and our relationship with risk, with a focus on the relationship that we have adjacent to him. Frozen in the midst of action, caught between the potential of danger and the safety of prevention, the Caution Man reflects our own perpetual state of motion and anticipation, our own lack of stability, striving to exist in a constant middle, where our actions do not confront us and neither do they lay flat in front of our eyes. We too are caught never fully reaching resolution, but always navigating the tension of what might be. The Caution Man, with his outstretched arms and dynamic posture, reminds us that our lives, like his, are defined by the ongoing, ungraspable pursuit of safety, understanding, and meaning.

Through his suffering, this silhouette has proven to serve humanity in ways we do not rightfully consider, even in our pastime games, the hanged-man loses limbs as a result of our mistakes.

The Caution Man is more than a utilitarian figure; he is a vessel through which we interrogate our own proximities to failure, to anticipation, and to the spectrality of life as representation. His posture, eerily human yet flattened to serve, resonates with the ideas of the Uncanny, and recalls the expressive strain of Bernini's saints, and of Opie's abstracted walkers. But unlike those figures, the Caution Man is not posed by a human hand for the sake of beauty or tragedy, his form is engineered for the grammar of interruption. For the sake of becoming a semicolon to a sentence, the Caution Man stops us in our tracks, as we stand static in anticipatory stillness.

His ontology is ambiguous. If we consider, with Saussure, that the sign is arbitrary but anchored in social agreement, the Caution Man functions as a signifier unmoored from individual identity, stabilized only by collective recognition. Yet the trust we place in him betrays something deeper, the compulsion to animate the inanimate, to anthropomorphize precaution, to project feeling onto flatness, onto those beings which do not have to bear the torment of active questioning and thought. We want to share the burden of sentience and consciousness with those we've created ourselves. The Caution Man becomes both a threshold and a question. What are we when confronted by him? Who is to say we are not *him*, we too are posterised beings in cosmic wait for meaning.

Through this figure, we confront the idea that, while we may never fully escape the uncertainties we face, it is in our awareness and anticipation of them that we find a semblance of control and purpose. The

Caution Man may lack sentience in our realm, but it is uncertain whether or not he breathes among figures that embody his own dimension. Perhaps we too are figures stretched laterally across time, grazing meaning without edges, glimpsed only in the moment before recognition.

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